

Voltammetric studies of copper(II)-dithiocarbamate reaction and a differential pulse polarographic method for the determination of dithiocarbamates

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Abstract : The electrochemical behaviour of the reactions of dithiocarbamates with copper(II) in acetonitrile has been studied by both cyclic voltammetry and pulse polarography. The observations/data resulting from above studies has been found extremely useful not only in arriving out at a convincing mechanism for this analytically useful reaction, but also in evolving a remarkably sensitive differential pulse polarographic method for the determination of dithiocarbamates.

Keywords : Dithiocarbamates, copper(II), cyclic voltammetry, pulse polarography.

Dithiocarbamates (dics) find extensive use as agricultural fungicides and vulcanization accelerators (in the rubber industry) and consequently their determination has received much attention¹⁻⁴. In our efforts to evolve convenient, reliable and cost-effective methods for the analysis of dics, we found their reaction with copper(II) in acetonitrile to be of considerable analytical usefulness. The ease with which these compounds are smoothly and quantitatively oxidized by this reagent prompted us to evolve potentiometric and spectrophotometric methods for their determinations⁵. The most attractive features of these methods is excellent solution stability and enhanced oxidative power of reagent in acetonitrile. In our efforts to explore the mechanistic and analytical aspects of this reaction in a better way, we found that when pulse polarography was used in conjunction with cyclic voltammetry (cv), these techniques not only provided us a convincing mechanism for this reaction but at the same time a remarkably sensitive method emerged as a result of this study. The electrochemical response of copper(II) reagent at the electrode surface and the effect of dithiocarbamates on it provided useful informations in achieving the above objectives.

Results and discussion

The cv study of copper(II)-dithiocarbamate (dte) reaction in acetonitrile in the range 1.5 V to -0.2 V using platinum-silver/silver chloride electrode assembly and tetraethylammonium perchlorate (TEAP) as supporting electrolyte revealed that dics did not exhibits any current

peak either in forward or reverse scan. Copper(II) perchlorate, on the other hand, exhibited peaks, both in forward scan (E_{pc} , 815 mV) and reverse scan (E_{pa} , 1046 mV) (Fig. 1). The most interesting observations were made when dte (in acetonitrile) was gradually added to copper(II) and progress of reaction monitored quantitatively. Whereas both the peaks due to copper(II) reagent showed a gradual decrease in current intensity, two new peaks, one in the range at 366-439 mV (in the forward scan) and the other in the range at 438-507 mV (in the reverse scan) appeared simultaneously and each showed corresponding proportional increases in its current intensity. This behaviour continued till copper(II)-dte molar ratio 1 : 1 was reached. At this point, both the peaks due to copper(II) reagent disappeared completely but the other two peaks attained their full current intensities (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Typical cyclic voltammogram of copper(II) perchlorate at a platinum electrode.

Fig. 2. Typical cyclic voltammogram obtained as a result of the reaction of di-n-butylthiocarbamate with copper(II) perchlorate at platinum electrode.

The important cv characteristics of copper(II)-dtc reaction are given in Table 1. That the electrode process is diffusion-controlled, is evident from the data showing direct proportionality between peak current I_{pc} or I_{pa} and \sqrt{v} (v = scan rate). The data pertaining to copper(II)-sodium dimethyldithiocarbamate reaction is given in Table 2. The other dtcs show identical behaviours with regard to these reactions with copper(II) in acetonitrile.

The above changes in the cyclic voltammograms resulting from copper(II)-dtc reaction indicate that the above reaction proceeds through the formation of a new product, most plausibly, copper(III) dithiocarbamate complex. It is this product which undergoes reduction in the forward

Table 1. Cyclic voltammetric parameters for dithiocarbamates in the presence of copper(II) perchlorate (1 : 1 molar ratio) in acetonitrile

Dithiocarbamate	E_{pc} (mV)	E_{pa} (mV)	ΔE (mV)	E^0 (mV)
$R_2N.CS.S.Na$ 'R'				
Dimethyl	372	443	71	407
Diethyl	439	507	68	473
Di-n-propyl	383	441	58	412
Di-n-butyl	376	446	70	411
Di-n-pentyl	366	438	72	402
Di-n-benzyl	370	440	70	405

Table 2. Effect of scan rate on peak current of sodium dimethyldithiocarbamate in the presence of copper(II) perchlorate (1 : 1 molar ratio) in acetonitrile

Scan rate, v (mV s ⁻¹)	\sqrt{v}	I_{pc} (μA)	I_{pa} (μA)
20	4.8	0.98	0.98
30	5.5	1.18	1.16
50	7.1	1.54	1.50
80	8.9	1.94	1.90
100	10.0	2.18	2.12
120	10.9	2.38	2.32
150	12.3	2.70	2.58
200	14.1	3.08	2.96

scan and oxidation in the reverse scan and in doing so, it involves one-electron change ($\Delta E_p = E_{pc} - E_{pa}$: 58–72 mV, Table 1).

The formation of copper(III) dithiocarbamate complexes through the reaction of thiuram disulphides (the oxidation product of dithiocarbamates (1) and copper(I)) perchlorate is well known^{6,7}. That the above reaction indeed proceeds through the formation of complexes of type (2) has recently been established voltammetrically in our laboratory⁸. The role of perchlorate ion (a bulky anion) in stabilizing higher oxidation state of metals especially copper(III) dithiocarbamate complexes, is also quite well known⁹. Further support to the above mechanism is provided by IR spectrum of 2 (acetonitrile solution) which shows two bands at 1070 nm and 620 cm⁻¹ indicating the presence of perchlorate group in the ionic form i.e. outside coordination sphere and the appearance of additional band at 460 cm⁻¹ (not present in the spectrum of sodium dimethyldithiocarbamate) reveals the formation of Cu^{III}-S bond.

The successful use of cyclic voltammetry in elucidating the mechanism of copper(II)-dtc reaction prompted us to study this reaction by pulse polarography as well and to explore the feasibility of evolving a method for the determination of dithiocarbamates based on the above reaction. The pulse polarographic study of the above reaction in acetonitrile has been made using dropping mer-

Fig. 3. Typical differential pulse polarogram of copper(II) at 22 ± 1 °C : (1) supporting electrolyte, (2) copper(II) perchlorate at DME.

Fig. 4. Typical differential pulse polarogram obtained as a result of reaction of dithiocarbamates with copper(II) at 22 ± 1 °C : (1) supporting electrolyte, (2) di-n-butyl dtc at DME.

cury electrode (DME) as the working electrode, saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as reference electrode, platinum wire as an auxiliary electrode and TEAP as a supporting electrolyte. Copper(II) perchlorate (in acetonitrile) yielded a well-defined, diffusion-controlled peak at -300 mV (Fig. 3), dtcs gave the similar peaks in the range 204 – 286 mV. When a dtc (in acetonitrile) was added to copper(II), whereas peaks both due to dtc and copper(II) showed a gradual decrease in current intensity, a new peak (98 – 150 mV) with proportional increase in current intensity, appeared simultaneously. This trend continued till copper(II)-dtc molar ratio of $1 : 1$ was achieved. At this point, whereas peaks due to both copper(II) and dtc disappeared completely, the new peak attained maximum current intensity (Fig. 4, Table 3). It needs to be mentioned here that if either dtc or copper(II) exceeds the above $1 : 1$ molar ratio, it starts giving its own respective peaks. It is interesting to mention here that though the peak due to dtcs (204 – 286 mV) alone could be used for

the determination of a particular dtc but amazingly, the new peak (98 – 150 mV) obtained as a result of above reaction, showed approximately five times more sensitivity than the one obtained due to dtc alone. This prompted us to evolve a sensitive differential pulse polarographic method for determination of dithiocarbamates. The determination has been made on the basis of calibration graphs drawn between concentration of dtc (μg) (added to copper(II) reagent) and peak current (μA). Using the straight line equation $y = mx + c$, the slope and intercept values have been determined (Table 3). The listed dtcs with sample sizes 1 and $4 \mu\text{g}$ have been determined with maximum relative standard deviation (RSD) of 0.95% (Table 4).

Acetonitrile has been a solvent of choice in the present studies because of the following reasons : (i) it is resistant to oxidation or reduction, (ii) it has a high dielectric constant thereby facilitating the solubility of dtcs and (iii) copper(II) perchlorate shows enhanced oxidation

Table 3. Differential pulse polarographic and calibration parameters for dithiocarbamates in the presence of copper(II) perchlorate ($1 : 1$ molar ratio) in acetonitrile

Dithiocarbamate	As such E_{pc} (mV)	In the presence of copper(II) perchlorate E_p (mV) (-ve)	Linearity range ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	Slope	Intercept
Dimethyl	275	150	4.8	0.2101	-0.0040
Diethyl	230	110	5.2	0.2114	0.0007
Di-n-propyl	264	114	5.5	0.2217	-0.0040
Di-n-butyl	245	105	5.8	0.1937	-0.0026
Di-n-pentyl	286	98	6.2	0.1452	-0.0080
Di-n-benzyl	258	135	6.4	0.1809	0.0033

Table 4. Differential pulse polarographic determination of dithiocarbamates using copper(II) perchlorate

Dithiocarbamate R ₂ N.CS.S.Na 'R'	Amount taken = 1.0 µg		Amount taken = 4.0 µg	
	Mean peak current, i_p (µA)	Amount found (µg)	Mean peak current, i_p (µA)	Amount found (µg)
Dimethyl	0.207	0.992 ± 0.005	0.834	3.96 ± 0.023
Diethyl	0.210	0.991 ± 0.004	0.848	4.02 ± 0.031
Di-n-propyl	0.220	0.992 ± 0.009	0.886	3.98 ± 0.020
Di-n-butyl	0.192	0.994 ± 0.008	0.772	3.97 ± 0.038
Di-n-pentyl	0.144	1.005 ± 0.007	0.579	3.98 ± 0.024
Di-n-benzyl	0.182	0.996 ± 0.006	0.730	4.01 ± 0.018

behaviour and remarkable solution stability in acetonitrile^{10,11}.

Experimental

Acetonitrile (Merck) was kept over phosphorus(V) oxide (5 g L⁻¹) and distilled twice. Tetraethylammonium perchlorate was prepared by the reported method¹². Its standardized solution (0.01 M in acetonitrile) was prepared by dissolving 0.2296 g of the compound in one litre of acetonitrile. Sodium salts of dimethyl, diethyl, di-n-propyl, di-n-butyl, di-n-pentyl and di-n-benzyl dithiocarbamic acids were prepared and purified by known methods^{13,14}. A standard solution of copper(II) perchlorate, Cu(ClO₄)₂·2H₂O, in acetonitrile was prepared by method as described earlier¹⁵. Triton X-100 (Merck), 0.002% solution in acetonitrile was used as suppressor.

The polarographic measurements were made with an Elico (India) Pulse Polarograph (Model CL-90) equipped with DME as working electrode, SCE as reference electrode and coiled platinum wire as an auxiliary electrode. Cyclic voltammetry was carried out with a ECDA-001 Electrochemical System (Con-Serv Enterprise, Mumbai). A platinum disc electrode as working electrode and Ag/AgCl (0.01 M in methanol) as reference electrode were used. A platinum wire was used as an auxiliary electrode. All the polarography and cyclic voltammetry experiments were done in an inert atmosphere achieved by purging the cell solution with pure nitrogen for 5 min. All experiments were performed at 23°.

Cyclic voltammetry procedure :

2.0 ml each of copper(II) perchlorate (0.01 M in acetonitrile) and a dithiocarbamate (also 0.01 M in acetonitrile) were taken separately in electrochemical cells and volume made to 5 ml with TEAP (0.01 M in acetonitrile). The cyclic voltammograms of each solution were recorded with the following instrumental parameters; initial potential = 1500 mV; final potential = -200 mV;

scan rate = 100 mV s⁻¹; current sensitivity = 0.01 mA.

Aliquots ranging from 0.1–2.0 ml of acetonitrile solution (0.01 M) of each dithiocarbamate were taken in electrochemical cells with each cell containing 2.0 ml of copper(II) perchlorate (0.01 M) in acetonitrile and final volume made to 5 ml with TEAP (0.01 M in acetonitrile). The cyclic voltammograms of each solution was recorded with the above instrumental parameters.

Pulse polarography procedure :

5.0 ml each of copper(II) perchlorate (0.001 M in acetonitrile) and a dithiocarbamate (also 0.001 M in acetonitrile) were taken separately in 5.0 ml glass stoppered flasks and diluted to 20 ml with acetonitrile. Each solution was then mixed 20 ml TEAP (0.01 M in acetonitrile), 2 ml Triton X-100 (0.002%) and final volume made to 50 ml with TEAP. The polarograms of each solution was recorded with following instrumental parameters; initial potential = 400 mV; drop time = 1 s; pulse amplitude = 50 mV; sensitivity = 1 µA/V; x-axis = 100 mW/cm; and y-axis = 200 mV/cm (on polarocard).

Aliquots (0.1–2.0 ml) of acetonitrile solution (10⁻³ M) of each dithiocarbamate were taken in polarographic cells containing 5.0 ml of copper(II) perchlorate (0.001 M in acetonitrile) and volume made to 20 ml with acetonitrile. The differential pulse polarograms of each solution was recorded in the same manner as described above. Calibration graphs were constructed by plotting peak current (µA) versus concentration of dtc (µg) added to copper(II).

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